

Artificial Reef: National Treasure

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ABSTRACT

The Blue Amazon is a vast maritime area in the South Atlantic, home to unexplored natural resources and rich biodiversity. This region has immeasurable potential for the production and export of bioproducts, contributing to the country's productive autonomy. An interesting strategy for preserving this ecosystem is the development of artificial marine reefs through the dismantling of old ships. This approach not only conserves the marine environment, but also generates areas of environmental protection, promoting development and national wealth. The correct disposal of old ships is an important practice for maritime safety, considering the marking of sunken hulls on nautical charts and the promotion of environmental reserve areas. Artificial reefs inserted in the aquatic environment provide the necessary substrate for the development of a biological community, simulating what occurs in natural reefs. These structures provide habitats for marine life and can be used for scientific research, extraction of raw materials for bioproducts, sustainable diving sites and revitalization of biologically degraded areas, as well as helping to combat coastal erosion.

Keywords: Blue Bioproduct, Brazilian Productive Autonomy, Artificial Ship Reefs.

1. INTRODUCTION

The controlled sinking of ships in designated areas to create artificial reefs extends the life of the vessel, giving it an environmentally friendly destination.

These structures provide for the revitalization of the environment, attract species and become habitat for a vast marine biodiversity (Ormond et al., 1997, p.449).

Areas degraded by industrial trawling will be revitalized as reefs will grow on top of and around the structure. The artificial ship reef enables the creation of nature reserves and defends the sustainable use of environmental resources (BRASIL, 2020).

The dismantling of ships to create artificial reefs is an ecologically sustainable strategy, making it a strategy for advancing research in the areas of Marine Science and Technology. In the rich biodiversity invigorated on the artificial ship reefs, species of marine sponges produce substances with pharmaceutical potential. Other marine organisms have bioactive compounds, which serve as a source for research into drugs, such as antibiotics and antitumors (Nogueira, 2017).

Reefs are true treasures of biodiversity and can lead to the discovery of new enzymes and pigments. The lodging in these structures of calcareous algae makes it possible to extract anti-fouling substances and others with applications in various areas. This contributes to Brazilian autonomy in the production of bioproducts (Nogueira, 2017).

These artificial structures play a key role in providing valuable substances for the sustainable production of bioproducts. As described by Nogueira (2017), among these substances, food products, application in the cosmetic industry and also have application in the textile industry. And according to BRASIL (2020), the protection of resources is a national strategy in the preservation of the ecosystems of the Blue Amazon, directing the country in the global growth of the bioeconomy.

This approach aims not only at the conservation of marine resources, but also at the sustainable use of these assets for economic and environmental benefit.

The Blue Amazon, with all its richness and immense biodiversity, must adopt strategies to restoration to save these marine ecosystems. According to BRASIL (1988), it is essential to protect and preserve the oceans for present and future generations. Reefs are the largest living structure on the planet and are threatened by climate change, rising temperatures, and pollution. It is estimated that by 2050 up to 90% of coral reefs could be lost if we do not act.

2. GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Revitalize the Blue Amazon with artificial reefs from old ships for bioproduct extraction.

2.1. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Create artificial reefs on the Brazilian coast by promoting environmental protection areas;
- Give an environmentally correct destination to old or abandoned ships;
- Promote the maritime mindset with sustainable diving;
- Leverage the Brazilian bioeconomy;
- Encourage scientific research to produce bioproducts.

2.2. SHIP ARTIFICIAL REEFS

Artificial reefs are structures implanted in the marine environment, contributing to the increase of biodiversity. As White et al. (1990) described, these structures allow marine organisms such as corals, algae and sponges to find attachment sites.

According to Mead & Black (2002), artificial reefs offer shelter for various marine organisms (fish and crustaceans), serve as tools to develop activities such as fishing, recreational diving and planned structure for surfing.

As Whitmarsh et al. (2008) described, artificial reefs serve as a home for other marine species, contributing to the health of marine ecosystems.

Lukens (1997) describes the different materials used in the manufacture of artificial reefs, among the varieties we highlight: tires, concrete blocks or sunken ships.

Each artificial reef structure has its particularities and can generate several factors, resulting in positive and negative points to the marine environment.

Recycled tires, when used as artificial reefs, represent a significant source of plastic pollution in the oceans and have harmful consequences.

As the tires wear out, they release small pieces of synthetic plastic, known as microplastics. These particles can have noticeable effects on marine animals causing, choking and intestinal obstruction (Collins et al., 2002).

In addition to causing pollution, tires degrade faster compared to concrete material, they also do not offer as much space as ships. As Collins et al. (2002) described, tires and concrete structures release chemical compounds, and are not an ecologically sustainable alternative.

Concrete blocks are expensive to produce, require proper transportation and positioning, and may not be as aesthetically interesting as sunken ships. As described by Chou (1997), founding decommissioned ships to create artificial reefs has several environmental and social benefits. This transforms the marine environment into an underwater sanctuary, where marine life flourishes and biomass production increases.

Diving into sunken ship environments is more fascinating because:

"The hull of the ship emerges covered in colorful sponges and vibrant corals. Fish swim around the portholes, as if exploring the caves and bulkheads, the salting undulates gently creating an ethereal scenery. Corals, once small fragments, now cling to metal surfaces, forming underwater gardens, where schools of fish circulate finding shelter in empty compartments." "Source: Prepared by the authors."

As Polovina (1991) describes, this environment becomes attractive for areas used by divers, who witness the magic that happens when man and the ocean meet in an eternal embrace.

“The sunken ship, once a symbol of strength and movement, is now an oasis of life. Every detail tells a story, the hatches that once opened for eager sailors, the currents that held heavy anchors, become the scene of enchantment in the depths of the ocean.” "Source: Prepared by the authors."

Decommissioned ships, such as tugboats, can continue to contribute to marine life even after their retirement. While their commercial lifespan hovers around 30 years, like reefs, they can collaborate for much longer.

As they described, the planned sinking of a ship contributes:

“In the preservation of the oceans, offering a new habitat for marine species, especially in areas with sandy bottoms where natural fixation is difficult. Artificial ship reefs are more attractive to fish than natural reefs, increasing marine biodiversity.” (ARENA et al., 2007)

According to White et al. (1990), demersal artificial reefs in shallow tropical waters increase the primary production of algae and invertebrates, increasing the natural habitat to support greater fish biomass.

The technique of artificially creating reefs with ships can boost underwater tourism, generating revenue for local communities and encouraging sustainable fishing.

As Steimle & Meier (1997) have described, it is necessary to:

That managers of artificial reef projects know the activities related to fishing, as it becomes a relevant ecological issue for the objectives of the projects. Artificial reefs play an important role in marine conservation, and they need to be managed sustainably to protect biodiversity and marine ecosystems.

In 2020, the Federal Government of Brazil proposed the establishment of artificial reefs on the Brazilian coast in environmental protection areas, approved by the Brazilian Navy.

The legislation for the creation of artificial reefs can be found in IBAMA's Normative Instruction No. 22, of July 10, 2009. which provides for environmental licensing for the installation of artificial reefs. According to section I, the scope of:

Article 2. The implementation of artificial reefs in the Brazilian Territorial Sea and in the Exclusive Economic Zone will have the following purposes: management of the use of fishing resources with a view to production, planning and support for fishing and aquaculture; conservation or restoration of biodiversity and degraded habitats; scientific research; waterfront protection or erosion control; recreational diving; elaboration of artificial bottoms aiming at the conformation of waves for the practice of nautical sports (IBAMA Normative No. 22/2009).

In the Blue Amazon, the creation of artificial reefs provides a suitable environment for marine life to establish and thrive. In addition to restoring degraded ecosystems, reefs contribute to the diversity of species and the health of the oceans.

Finally, deactivated ships as artificial reefs is a valuable strategy for preserving the environment, for the conservation of marine ecosystems, for sustainable development and advancement in scientific research in the Blue Amazon.

2.3. SHIPWRECK ENCHANTED REEF (SOURCE: BY CARDOSO, C. CAP)

From bow to stern, at the bottom of the sea, all its wrecks like lindeira, are storytellers in each hull of steel or wood.

The shipwrecks rest imposingly on the bottom of the endless sea, where the deck turns into a garden. Covered with corals, sponges and algae become Sunday docks.

The seabed with sunken reefs is a never-ending voracious spectacle, assimilated to the narwhal ivory tusks.

In the blue of the ocean, lives a sovereign world. Fish dance in harmony, each being has its symphony. In an extraordinary ballet, shoals paint the scenery. As musical notes we find refugee reef fish in the portholes and ancestral holds.

The old ship that braved the rough sea, is now a portal to a monumental underwater world. Even the mast revitalizes the ocean floor with organic bioproduct.

Once fearless navigators, they now harbor secrets and endless mysteries. The fearless shipwrecked enchants with praise.

His infinite majesty contemplates life as painite. Each shipwreck is a chapter of the past, which the wind sowed at will, becoming a witness to the storm.

Under filtered light, the dead works come to life, transforming themselves into scenarios of color images. The rusty hull and the rudder worn out by the shipwrecked time now tell stories, eternalizing glories.

Their names whispered by the chains become shelter, as guardians of the abyss is pure exhibition. The shipwrecks, like artificial reefs, remind us that the sea is an endless graveyard, creating an indescribably beautiful scenery.

Forgotten sailors are more than sunk, stranded or abandoned metal and wood. They are treasures, submerged poems, like the organic beauty of the entire ocean depth.

The sea creatures, the secrets of the waves, and the sense of belonging to the ocean connect us deeply with our nature. We come from the sea, salt water is our home.

The waves whisper secrets that are our plots. Our roots plunged into the depths, fullness and fortitude emerge.

In navigated art we find our true home. The oceans present us with pearls of wisdom, in it we find the essence of full realization with mastery.

We are part of this vast ocean forming a sovereign people, the sea sustains, the ocean feeds us.

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2.3.1. SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH METHOD

The research method developed was through the bibliographic approach, involving the search, selection and analysis of written sources, books, scientific articles and documents. The objective was to obtain information about the environmental benefits and the consequences in the process of dismantling old ships to create artificial reefs. This strategy aims to contribute to the revitalization of marine ecosystems and promote the sustainable use of the Blue Amazon.

The dismantling of ships provides a purpose to vessels that are no longer viable for commercial use. This is a way of giving a useful end to ships after they are no longer useful to the market.

The anchoring of the ship at sea involves challenges, and must be monitored by environmental specialists. In addition to knowing the environment in which the ship must be anchored, it is necessary to perform detailed calculations to determine the center of gravity, inclination and ideal speed for the ship to sink safely.

To choose the best location, it is essential to consider the following factors:

- The site must be of adequate depth for the sunken vessel, allowing it to become submerged and become part of the reef.
- It is important that the site is accessible for divers and tourists interested in exploring the artificial reef.
- The reef must be at a safe distance from the shore to avoid navigation hazards and environmental impacts.
- Artificial reefs should be placed in areas with favorable conditions for marine life. The conditions of currents, waves and visibility must be analyzed.
- Locations should be chosen where marine biodiversity can benefit from the artificial reef. Areas with little marine life may not be ideal.
- The local regulations and permits required to sink the vessel.
- Consider the environmental impact of sinking, such as the removal of polluting materials and proper preparation of the vessel. Each location has its particularities, and a careful evaluation is essential for the success of the anchoring project.

2.3.2. RESULTS

By revitalizing the Blue Amazon with artificial reefs from old ships, we will be contributing to the conservation of marine biodiversity.

Considering the importance of IBAMA's Normative Instruction No. 22, of July 10, 2009. There is a need to create artificial reefs to encourage scientific research and develop the economy through the extraction of bioresources.

In addition to encouraging studies on the production of bioproducts, monitoring these ecosystems is essential. SisGAAz, by monitoring artificial reefs, offers opportunities for scientific studies. It is possible to observe the growth of organisms, evaluate the effectiveness of reefs and better understand marine ecosystems.

Turning abandoned vessels into artificial reefs is a strategy that provides an environmentally friendly destination for ships that can no longer sail. This justification is supported by Complementary Law No. 97 of June 1999, which states: "it is up to the Navy, as private subsidiary attributions, to contribute to the formulation and conduct of national policies that concern the sea" (BRASIL, 1999).

In this way, opportunities are created for marine life, mitigating environmental impacts and converging sustainable rational use, generating the development of bioresources in the Blue Amazon.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Considering the principles established in IBAMA's Normative Instruction No. 22, of July 10, 2009. For the sustainable and efficient exploitation of the resources of the Blue Amazon, an effective strategy is the development of marine artificial reefs through the anchoring of old ships.

Artificial reefs can be created from controlled shipwrecks, transforming ship hulls into habitats for a diversity of marine plants and animals. In addition to contributing to the preservation of the marine environment, they offer opportunities for the extraction of bioproducts, such as algae and other organisms, which can be used in the production of medicines and food.

Therefore, revitalizing the Blue Amazon with artificial reefs from old vessels is a promising strategy to promote the development and sustainable use of bioresources. Finally, the creation of artificial reefs from the dismantling of ships is in line with sustainable development and can be seen as a positive innovation in the naval area.

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First of all, we thank the Creator of the Universe, because without Him nothing would be possible. Lord, who in your lives have manifested a predilection for the sea.

Make us learn the lesson of the waves, that each of our retreats may be an effort for our advancement. In the hour of storm, give us faith in your power over the waves and the winds. Show us that with you there is no shipwreck.

May our faith be like a beacon, which even in the face of storms, remains unshaken, and guides us on the paths with its light.

Make us see the right direction in our lives, leading our hand to the helm, so that we arrive at the port of infinite peace with infinite joy. Amen!

You are the lord of the seas and the winds, of the earth and of the stars.

You are the lighthouse, the light that never goes out.

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